

Hommage à Klaus Nomi — Olga Neuwirth

Julie Delisle, 2019

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<https://timbreandorchestration.org/writings/amazing-moments-in-timbre/2019/2/28/hommage-klaus-nomi>

The Amazing Moments in Timbre series continues with a piece by Olga Neuwirth. Known as the "Enfant terrible" of the Austrian contemporary classical music scene, Neuwirth composes in a very theatrical and expressionist way, and describes her own art as a music of catastrophes ("Katastrophenmusik"). In her *Hommage à Klaus Nomi* (2009), for countertenor and chamber ensemble, she magnifies Klaus Sperber (also known as Klaus Nomi), an iconic queer singer known for mixing New Wave aesthetics with operatic elements, in a set of four songs (*So Simple*, *Remember*, *Can't help it*, and *The Witch*).

The first song is a reprise of *Simple Man*, by Kristian Hoffmann, as sung by Klaus Nomi. Here, the accompaniment of the original version has been re-orchestrated, using clarinet, trumpet, electric guitar, cello, and double bass in addition to the synthesizers, to create colorful effects that enhance the expressivity of the countertenor part.

Klaus Nomi, *Simple Man* (1982 - original version): <https://youtu.be/E2ctfocMqHs>

Olga Neuwirth, *Hommage à Klaus Nomi* (2009), *So Simple* (excerpt), with Andrew Watts (countertenor) and Klangforum Wien (June 4, 2005): https://medias.ircam.fr/x099ae8_hommage-a-klaus-nomi-olga-neuwirth

Works Cited

Olga Neuwirth, *Hommage à Klaus Nomi* (2009), *So Simple* (excerpt), with Andrew Watts (countertenor) and Klangforum Wien (June 4, 2005): https://medias.ircam.fr/x099ae8_hommage-a-klaus-nomi-olga-neuwirth